
Research

Ghana's path to sustainable development: Evading the middle-income trap (MIT)

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Abstract: This paper seeks to highlight the stumbling blocks on the path to Sustainable Development and suggest how Ghana could address these challenges it faces in order to avoid being caught in the middle-income trap. Ghana's development agenda has been a priority for the country since its independence in 1957. At the time of independence, the Ghanaian economy was handed into the hands of indigenous leaders to drive the country towards prosperity. Ghana has since been on a continuum of slow advancement. Currently, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) stands at USD 69.76 billion (2020), as the nation strives toward the attainment of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted in 2015. Ghana was the first country to meet the 1st Millennium Development Goal (MDG1) in Sub-Saharan Africa by reducing poverty by half. That notwithstanding, people continue to live in abject poverty in most rural areas (especially in the northern regions of the country). This shows that Ghana must embrace sound policies and adjustments in order to overcome such developmental challenges. By reviewing the literature on what accounts for poor economic growth, the middle-income trap (MIT), and the plausible ways of escaping this trap, the paper seeks to provide an advisory note on how Ghana and other low-income countries (LICs) alike could achieve sustainable growth and endeavor to avoid the middle-income trap (MIT). The paper argues that through good governance and institutions, Inclusive Growth, Infrastructural Investment, and economic transformation, Ghana could address her developmental challenges and avoid being caught up in the middle-income trap.

Keywords: Ghana, development, middle-income trap, clean growth, inclusive growth, industrialization, sustainable growth

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Accepted: 29 July, 2022; **Published:** 02 August, 2022

How to cite this article: Owusu, G., & Aglago, A. (2022) *Ghana's path to sustainable development: Evading the middle-income trap (MIT)*.

North American Academic Research, 5(7), 57-75. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6951166>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

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Introduction

Ghana goes to the IMF for economic bailout for the second time in three years and at least the 17th time since joining the program in 1957.¹ Ghana sought the first IMF program in 1966 after the military overthrow of its first president, Dr. Kwame Nkrumah, at a time of severe economic hardship.² Since then, the fourth republic has been characterized by a cycle of IMF bailouts. The country’s recent program with the IMF ended in April 2019. Just three years after, the Ghanaian government is seeking yet another bailout from the IMF (in 2022). The economy of Ghana, like many developing economies, appears to be trapped in repeated cycles of economic downturns.

The Economy of Ghana comprises three key sectors: Agriculture, Industry, and Services sectors. Over the years the Agricultural sector has been dominant in the economy as it employs more than 50% of the active labor force. However, the contribution of this sector to GDP growth keeps falling due to the expansion of the services sector, particularly the financial sector. Ghana is a lower-middle-income country with a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) currently estimated at USD 77.59 billion (2020),³ with per capita of \$2,445.30 in 2020 (yet, one of the highest in West Africa). As an emerging economy, Ghana’s economy continued to expand in 2019 as the first quarter of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth was estimated at 6.7%, compared with 5.4% in the same period of the previous year, 2018. In addition, its growth in the non-oil sector was significantly improved—estimated at 6.0%. Apparently, the relatively high quarterly growth was driven by a strong recovery in the services sector, which grew by 7.2% compared with 1.2% in 2018.⁴ Ghana’s GDP per capita is currently estimated at 2084.64 US dollars in 2021—representing about 17% of the world’s average.⁵ The diagram below shows the pattern of GDP growth over the past three decades.

Ghana - Gross domestic product per capita (Dollars)

Source : IMF
 Date : 2015
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Figure 1: Ghana’s GDP per capita over the years

Source: IMF (2015)

¹ Citinewsroom, July 2, 2022. <https://citinewsroom.com/2022/07/bright-simons-writes-17-notes-in-ghanas-17th-imf-tune/amp/>

² IMF 2021. <https://www.imf.org/external/np/fin/tad/extarr2.aspx?memberKey1=350&date1key=2018-05-31>

³ World Bank 2021 <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?view=chart&locations=GH>

⁴ World Bank 2020 <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/ghana/overview>

⁵ Trading Economics 2020 <https://tradingeconomics.com/ghana/gdp-per-capita>

From the diagram above, the growth in national GDP has been significant in recent decades. The 227,540 Km² (87,854 sq. miles) land area of Ghana is occupied by a population of over a 32million people. The general demographics of Ghana depict the country to be youthful—with about 65 percent of the population between the ages of 0 and 45years. The youthful nature of Ghana’s population presents both hope and challenge for the country. Whereas the country hopes for an increasing labor force, it faces the need of providing the teeming youth with education, training, and jobs. Failing to meet the needs of this youthful population could spell doom for the future of Ghana and Africa at large.

Ghana is also known for the numerous natural resources that it possesses. Ghana is the world’s second-largest cocoa producer⁶ and the continent’s largest gold producer⁷. The country is also rich in silver, manganese, bauxite, timber, petroleum, limestone, industrial diamonds, and oil. The country mostly exports gold, petroleum, and cocoa mostly to India, China, and South Africa while most of its imports come from China, the United States of America, and Belgium. Ghana is one of the most peaceful and culturally rich countries in Africa. It has a beautiful blend of several ethnic and racial groups living together peacefully.

According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), Ghana has been classified in the Human Development category, with an HDI value of 0.596, ranking 142nd position out of 189 countries and territories. It observes that Ghana’s HDI value has increased by only 31.1% between 1990 and 2018.⁸ The high deficit in physical and social infrastructure has left most Ghanaians with low standards of living. Lack of access to health facilities, for example, has led to high maternal mortality and the rise in cases of diseases such as measles and tuberculosis. There is low life expectancy, low literacy rate, high maternal mortality, and less access to potable water and sanitation. According to the Ghana Statistical Service report of 2017, 6.8 million Ghanaians, representing 23.4 percent of the population, could not afford to spend more than GH¢4.82—approximately US\$1—a day in 2016/17.⁹ The figure below shows the human development index in Ghana over the years.

Figure 2: Ghana's human development index
Source: UNDP (2015)

⁶ World Bank 2020 <https://www.worldbank.org/en/data/statistical-capacity-building/data-innovation-fund/integrating-soil-mapping-into-cocoa-farm-development-plans-in-Ghana>

⁷ Forbes 2021 <https://www.forbes.com/sites/greatspeculations/2021/06/23/updated-top-10-gold-producing-countries/>

⁸ UNDP report, 2018.

⁹ Ghana Statistical Service. Ghana Living Standards Survey Round 7, (2017).

From the figure above, Ghana's human development indexes have been rising over the years. Even though Ghana has chalked relatively positive development (which promoted it to a lower-middle-income country in 2010) over the years, scholars like Ayelazuno, have observed the paradox between these economic indicators and the actual well-being of most Ghanaians— noting that the people “still suffer grinding poverty.”¹⁰ Indeed, there still remain areas in Ghana with a low level of education, inadequate health facilities, lack of potable drinking water, no access to good roads, and the existence of outmoded cultural practices. Cases of insecurity, poverty, corruption, and inequality among others continue to be prevalent in Ghana today. Nzeribe G. et al argue that African countries are still plagued by infra-structural deficits, corruption, insecurity, and inequalities.¹¹

Notwithstanding these challenges, Ghana has made remarkable strides in the past two or three decades in a multi-party democracy, which is regarded as one of the best democracies in the African region. The country has consistently ranked in the top three countries in Africa for freedom of speech and press freedom, over the years. For example, the World Bank has praised Ghana for strengthening its public procurement system with the Public Procurement Act 2003, making it one of the most comprehensive in the developing world.¹² This has accorded the country significant respect and recognition— a source of social capital. The West African country, Ghana, despite its huge potential, lags in various developmental indicators.

This paper aims to assess the factors that account for Ghana's relatively slow pace of development. It also explores the necessary reforms that could set the stage for sustained national development to help Ghana evade the dawning middle-income trap. Thus, the next section focuses on the methodology to explicate the conceptual framework, data collection, and analysis techniques used in the study. The third section presents the analyses and discussions of Ghana's developmental challenges. From the implications of the challenges, possible solutions are then recommended in the fourth section. The paper closes with a conclusion section that summarizes the main findings of the study.

Methodology/framework

This paper adopts a qualitative approach to analyze Ghana's developmental Challenges through the lens of the Middle-income trap model. The data used in this study come from the World Bank's country reports, International Monetary Fund reports, World Economic Forum reports, Ghana Statistical Service, news portals as well as relevant academic literature. With information from these sources, as well as the author's personal experience, a normative analysis is presented in the framework of the middle-income trap (MIT). The concept of the “middle-income trap” is useful in analyzing the dynamics of economic growth as it conforms to the framework of the mainstream economic growth theories.¹³

The Middle-income Trap

It is one thing “developing” and it is another “sustaining” it. This has been one of the major problems of most countries including Ghana. Development is defined as ‘an evolutionary process in which the human capacity increases in terms of initiating new structures, coping with problems, adapting to continuous change, and striving purposefully

¹⁰ Ayelazuno, J. Abembia. "Neoliberalism and Growth without Development in Ghana: A Case for State-led Industrialization." *Journal of Asian and African Studies* 49 (2013): 80-99.

¹¹ Nzeribe, Geraldine, et al. "Developmental challenges of African Developing Economies." 10 (2019): 53-80.

¹² World Bank, 2006.

¹³ Cai, F. Is There a “Middle-income Trap”? Theories, Experiences and Relevance to China. *China & World Economy*, 20: 49-61. 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-124X.2012.01272.x>

and creatively to attain new goals (Peet, 1999 cited in Du Pisani, 2006),¹⁴ whereas sustainability means a capacity to maintain some entity, outcome or process over time.¹⁵ As part of Ghana's quest to become a world-class country, it has joined 192 other countries to pursue SDGs or Global Goals, which are a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity by 2030. With effect from January 2016, the SDGs aim to foster economic growth, ensure social inclusion and protect the environment.

In 2014, the World Bank classified countries with GNI per capita of \$1,045 or less as low-income whereas those with GNI per capita between \$1,046 and \$4,125 are classified as lower-middle-income countries. Higher middle-income countries are those with between \$4,126 and \$12,745 GNI per capita while countries above \$12,745 are rated as high-income countries. Ghana qualified as a middle-income country as its GNI per capita hit more than \$1,045 in 2011.¹⁶ Felipe et al. (2012), came out with his classification which was based on GDP per capita but with different ranges. He classified lower-middle-income to be between \$2,000 and \$7,250.

From the second half of the nineteenth century, quite several countries have achieved middle-income status through rapid growth. However, many of those countries could not become high-income economies. They are stuck in what is known as the "middle-income trap" (a term apparently coined by Gill, Kharas, et al. (2007)), generally characterized by a sharp deceleration in growth, following a period of sustained increases in per capita income.

Kharas et al capture the idea of the Middle-income Trap (MIT) as a situation in which "countries that avoided the poverty trap and grew to middle-income levels subsequently stagnate and fail to grow to advanced-country levels." At that stage, such countries are unable to compete either with low-income poor countries or with high-income advanced countries. According to Felipe et al. (2012), a country is "middle-income trapped" if the country is stuck in the lower-middle-income category for more than 28 years, or in the upper-middle-income for more than 14 years.

Scholars have identified some middle-income countries (MICs) such as South Africa, Brazil, Argentina, and India as having been caught in the Middle-income Trap (MIT). In their work, they offer strategies for low-income countries (LICs) to achieve growth and for middle-income economies to be able to escape the trap. According to the authors, low-income economies grow mainly by diversification and industrialization of cities in order to take care of rising urbanization—thus, the need to focus on supply (of labor). The strategies for middle-income economies, they argue, need to focus on demand, and build a more capital-intensive and skill-intensive economy.¹⁷ Wang and Lan argue that the 'fundamental drivers for an economy to escape the MIT' include 'productivity, growth, and structural transformation.'¹⁸ This means that underlying conditions that ensure productivity growth and structural transformation must be present.

¹⁴ Du Pisani, Jacobus A. "Sustainable development—historical roots of the concept." *Environmental sciences* 3, no. 2 (2006): 83-96.

¹⁵ Basiago, Andrew D. "Economic, social, and environmental sustainability in development theory and urban planning practice." *Environmentalist* 19, no. 2 (1998): 145-161.

¹⁶ World Bank 2014 [2014 World Bank Income Classifications: Kyrgyz Republic Becomes Lower Middle Income Country](#)

¹⁷ Kharas, Homi, and Harinder Kohli. "What Is the Middle Income Trap, Why Do Countries Fall into It, and How Can It Be Avoided?" *Global Journal of Emerging Market Economies*, vol. 3, no. 3, Sept. 2011, pp. 281–289, doi:10.1177/097491011100300302.

¹⁸ Wang, C. and J. Lan. *Inequality, Aging, and the Middle Income Trap*. ADBI Working Paper 785. Tokyo: Asian Development Bank Institute. (2017). Available: <https://www.adb.org/publications/inequality-aging-and-middle-income-trap>

Thus, this paper suggests **good governance and building of strong institutions; inclusive growth; 'planned' investment in 'advanced' infrastructure and economic transformation, diversification, and industrialization** in the context of 'clean' and 'green growth' as the basic requirement for such an economy as Ghana's.

Figure 3: The Middle-income Trap

Source: Asia 2050, Emerging Markets Forum

In the figure above, the three countries started at similar growth levels but after 1995 South Korea is seen to have beaten the middle-income trap, leaving behind Brazil and South Africa. Literature shows that various factors differ in those countries, hence resulting in the growth pattern above.¹⁹

Despite the overall good performance, the crucial question remains whether Ghana can reach high-income status and which policies it needs to implement to succeed. Stagnation in middle-income status often happens when countries are too rich to compete with low-cost producers elsewhere but too poor to invest in activities with higher value-added. Aiyar et al. (2013), opined that slowdown in middle-income countries tends to be more frequent than in low- and high-income countries. At the same time, however, a growth "slowdown" may be no more than a temporary phenomenon, which may lengthen the transition time to high-income status, but it is not necessarily synonym with being "trapped" in a low-growth state. Ghana has been battling with development problems since its colonial era through independence and until today. The country has seen some extent of economic growth due to the political stability it has enjoyed for the past two decades and improvement in its agricultural sector. However, despite the successes chalked in these sectors

¹⁹ Kharas et al, 2011; Daron Acemoglu and James Robinson, 2012; Berg and Ostry 2011

and other sectors of its economy, like most African countries, Ghana continues to face many developmental problems. The paper puts forth four ways for Ghana to evade the 'poverty trap,' move to an upper-middle-income status, and avoid the trap of middle-income economies.

Ghana's Development Sphinx: The Way Forward

Poor Governance and Corruption

To start with, Ghana faces the problem of **poor governance** characterized by weak institutions, corruption, and a lack of transparency, equity, and inclusion. Public sector corruption has been prevalent. The 2019 report by Transparency International ranked Ghana 80th among the countries with the least corruption—dropping from 78th position in 2017, with a score of 41 out of 100.²⁰ Ghana's anti-corruption campaign has not yielded the desired results over the years with an average score of 38.95 points between 1998 and 2019.²¹ Even though Ghana boasts of one of the notable icons of democracy on the African continent, various indicators of good governance are lacking.

Judging from the WGI's report on six composite dimensions of governance—"Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, and Control of Corruption"²²—Ghana lags in Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, and Control of Corruption. This has not only delayed the desired pace of national development but also, put the country in danger of stagnation and being caught in the so-called Middle-Income Trap (MIT). Knowing the gravity of damages corruption causes to Ghana, Gyimah-Boadi, E. (2002) sought to elaborate on various ways of combating corruption in Ghana and Africa at large. In his argument, Ghana has enough anti-corruption tools that could effectively fight corruption, but these tools lack enforcement.²³ According to Khan & Senhadji (2000), poor governance by African countries has led to poor economic growth since it affects negatively investment, productivity, foreign Aid, and consumption among others.

Ghana's Legal Instrument and Institutions for Fighting Corruption

Not as though Ghana lacks measures to tackle corruption; the constitution is ripe with various anti-corruption provisions. The fourth republic marked the shift in paradigm in the fight against corruption. Legislations and institutions are used under the fourth republic to fight corruption as opposed to commissions of inquiry and other draconian measures used prior to the Fourth Republican Era. Some legislations such as the Financial Administration Act, the Whistle Blowers Act, and the Internal Audit Agency Act, together with institutions such as the Public Accounts Committee of Parliament, CHRAJ, and EOCO as well as the role of civil society and the media have been the key legal instruments in Ghana's anti-corruption fight. Kututwa (2005) argued that the legal or legislative framework is the starting point in the fight against corruption.

The 1992 Constitutional and Anti-Corruption

Guided by history, the framers of the 1992 Constitution included several provisions which seek to guide against corruption, mismanagement of public resources, and promote accountability. First, in chapter six of the constitution on the directive principle of state policy, it is stated in Article 35(8) that—the state shall take steps to eradicate corrupt practices and the abuse of power (Republic of Ghana, 1992). The state may deem to have given meaning to this provision due to the numerous Acts of Parliament passed to regulate the management of public resources and the conduct

²⁰ Transparency International, 2019.

²¹ See Appendix 1

²² World Bank Report, 2017; www.govindicators.org

²³ Gyimah-Boadi, Emmanuel. *Confronting corruption in Ghana and Africa*. Vol. 4, no. 2. Ghana Center for Democratic Development, 2002.

of public officers. Article 37(1) of the Constitution also states that “the State shall endeavor to secure and protect a social order founded on the ideals and principles of freedom, equality, justice, probity, and accountability.”²⁴

Secondly, the constitution also establishes **independent constitutional bodies** with mandates which are targeted at ensuring that public resources are well managed, and accountability is maintained. One of such bodies is **the office of the Auditor-General** established under Article 187 of the constitution. The Auditor-General is mandated to audit the public accounts of Ghana and of all public offices. Also, the constitutions provided for the establishment of the Commission on Human Rights and Administrative Justice (CHRAJ) mandated under Article 218(a) to — investigate complaints of violations of fundamental rights and freedoms, injustice, corruption, abuse of power, and unfair treatment of any person by a public officer in the exercise of his official duties (Republic of Ghana,1992).

Moreover, chapter 24 of the constitution is dedicated to **the code of conduct for public officers**. Article 284 of the constitution states —A public officer shall not put himself in a position where his personal interest conflicts or is likely to conflict with the performance of the functions of his office. The chapter also provides for the declaration of assets and liabilities by public officers on the assumption of office, every four years, and upon leaving office.

All these constitutional provisions have been given a further boost through the numerous Acts of Parliament enacted since the coming into force of the Constitution.

Inequality and Socio-economic Deprivation

Again, the **socio-economic deprivations and high inequality** among various segments of Ghanaian society are a major setback on the county’s development path. As Nzeribe and others argue, Ghana, like many other African countries, is beset by social inequalities, poor infrastructure, unemployment, and abject poverty. Ghana has become an unequal country where the benefits of economic growth and poverty reduction are not equally distributed across the nation. In Ghana, only a few regions and cities benefit from the share of the national cake. Most rural and deprived communities are abandoned, some of which are because of political affiliations. The northern regions of Ghana, for example, face high levels of poverty, unemployment, diseases, and illiteracy. True to the argument put forth by Benhabib and Rustichini (1996), the high levels of inequality in Ghana have led to ‘socio-political instabilities’ in various areas of the country.²⁵ Indeed, the rising income disparities have led to low human capital development, low literacy rates, and high maternal mortality in various rural communities and slum cities alike. There is persistent gender disparity in access to the country’s resources. Ghana’s electoral and political system is male-dominated. Males are regarded as superior to females. The figure below is a summary of the inequalities between men and women in Ghana.

²⁴ Republic of Ghana, 1992 constitution

²⁵ Tribal wars abound in the poor northern regions of Ghana. See Bogner, Artur. "The 1994 civil war in northern Ghana: the genesis and escalation of a 'tribal' conflict." *Ethnicity in Ghana*. Palgrave Macmillan, London, 2000. 183-203.

Figure 4: Index between men and women in politics, education, labor domains, and legislation in Ghana.

In Figure 4 above, among all four variables, politics and legislation recorded a huge discrepancy between men and women in Ghana. According to the figure, more men attain education as compared to women, whereas the number of women in the labor force is almost equivalent to that of men.

Figure 5: Gini coefficient (measurement of dispersion in income inequality)

Source: Ghana Statistical Service

As shown in Figure 5 above, the Gini coefficient increased from 42.3% in 2012/2013 to 43.0% in 2016/2017. Also, access to potable water, health service, schools, commutable roads, and sanitary facilities is simply lacking in many communities in Ghana. Social deprivations abound in Ghana: some 6.8 million people, representing 23.4 percent of the population, could not afford to spend more than GH¢4.82 – approximately US\$1 – a day, according to the Ghana Statistical Service report, 2017.²⁶ This phenomenon has resulted in low productivity and hence poor growth.

²⁶ Ghana Statistical Service. Ghana Living Standards Survey Round 7, (2017).

Infrastructural Deficit

The global infrastructural gap requires approximately 4% of global GDP, equivalent to about US\$4tn annually.²⁷ Dobbs et al. (2013) project that by 2030, the global infrastructure gap would require an investment of US\$57tn– equivalent to about 3.5% of global GDP.²⁸ For developing countries with a high infrastructural financing gap, it is estimated that circa US\$1.5tn is needed annually to bridge the infrastructure gap.²⁹ The current state of infrastructural investment in Ghana is woefully inadequate to drive the desired economic growth.³⁰ Just as in several emerging economies, additional infrastructural investment is a sine qua non for socio-economic development.^{31 32} However, sub-Saharan African countries lag behind in critical infrastructure that could transform economies and drive socio-economic development.

High infrastructural deficit and poor urbanization management have been Ghana's challenges in attaining sustainable growth. Ghana lacks crucial infrastructure—both social and physical—that could set the tone for the rapid development it seeks. Also, the country has not been able to reap the benefits of urbanization because the inefficient management of urban centers and the lack of adequate infrastructure render the urban population less productive. This situation also makes the growth of Ghana's cities 'fragmented.'³³ Social infrastructure such as healthcare, education, transportation, public facilities, and recreation are difficult to access in various parts of the country. In the same vein, the physical infrastructures like hospitals, schools, commutable roads, and stadia, among others are woefully inadequate. For instance, "Schools Under Trees" has been a term in Ghana to describe schools conducted in dilapidated structures and under the shades of trees. This widens the inequality gap in Ghanaian society and contributes to the low Human Capital Development. According to an article published by World Bank, Ghana spends about \$1.2 billion per year on infrastructure, equivalent to about 7.5 percent of GDP. A further \$1.1 billion is lost each year to inefficiencies, notably underpricing of power. Ghana's annual infrastructure funding gap is about \$0.4 billion per year, related to power and water.³⁴ Greater economic activities are being hindered by a lack of adequate transport and communication systems as well as the inadequacy of water and energy infrastructure.

²⁷ Estache, Antonio, Tomas Serebrisky, and Liam Wren-Lewis. "Financing infrastructure in developing countries." *Oxford Review of Economic Policy* 31, no. 3-4 (2015): 279-304.

²⁸ Dobbs, Richard, H. Pohl, D. Lin, J. Mischke, N. Garemo, J. Hexter, S. Matzinger, R. Palter, and R. Nanavatty. "Infrastructure productivity: How to save \$1 trillion a year. McKinsey Global Institute." *McKinsey Co January* (2013).

²⁹ Solheim, Erik. "We can, and must, end poverty." (2013): 15-18.

³⁰ Owusu-Manu, De-Graft, Adam Braimah Jehuri, David John Edwards, Frank Boateng, and George Asumadu. "The impact of infrastructure development on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa with special focus on Ghana." *Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction* (2019).

³¹ Foster, Vivien, and Cecilia Briceño-Garmendia. *Africa's infrastructure: a time for transformation*. World Bank, 2010.

³² Calderón, César, and Luis Servén. "Infrastructure and economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa." *Journal of African Economies* 19, no. suppl_1 (2010): i13-i87.

³³ Larbi, Wordsworth Odame. "Spatial planning and urban fragmentation in Accra." *Third World Planning Review* 18.2 (1996): 193.

³⁴ World Bank <https://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi/abs/10.1596/1813-9450-5600>

Ghana’s Demographic Challenges

Ghana faces demographic challenges. As Ghana’s population surges, the country faces rising challenges in meeting the needs of a teeming youth. Currently, the country’s population is estimated at more than 32 million people.³⁵ The Dependency ratio of Ghana is estimated at 68.53% according to the World Bank (2018 est.). The proportion of Ghana’s population below 15 years has been between 47% and 48% since the early 1950s. The economically productive age group (those between ages 15 and 64), has been just under 50% of the total population, and those over 64 years old, about 3.0%. It would be rightly expected that these demographic trends would yield positive results, yet the inadequate social infrastructures, coupled with a lack of economic opportunities lead to high levels of unemployment which results in a high dependency burden on the working few. The high rate of unemployment and infrastructural deficit translates into poverty, social vices, and low productivity. Ghana’s youthful population faces an uncertain future in light of low access to education, training, and employment opportunities.

Number of unemployed people in Ghana from 2010 to 2022(in 1,000s)

Figure 6: Number of unemployed people in Ghana from 2010 to 2022(in 1,000s)

Source: Statista(2022)

In Figure 6, between 2021 and 2022, Ghana has reduced the number of its unemployed citizens by 9,000. The country experienced its peak of unemployment in 2015 when over 810,000 of its citizens were unemployed. Overall, the country’s unemployment rate has been on a downward trend. This survey was conducted on Ghanaians who were 15 years and older³⁶.

³⁵ Worldometer, 2020. <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/ghana-population/>

³⁶ Statista, 2022 [Ghana: number of unemployed people 2010-2022 | Statista](#)

Towards Sustainable Growth And Evading The Middle-Income Trap (MIT)

Looking at the above-discussed sustainable development challenges that Ghana faces, it will be prudent if the country can take drastic but strategic measures to prevent further underdevelopment and at the same time promote sustainable economic growth.

First, Ghana must embrace good governance and the building of strong institutions if it hopes for sustainable growth and a possible evasion of the Middle-Income Trap (MIT). A good governance structure must be adopted as a foundation for the implementation of development policy. Before that, the leadership of the country must possess a clear vision of the desired outcomes of those policies. The degree to which good governance played a role in poverty reduction over the period since the MDGs were adopted is debatable.³⁷ Daron Acemoglu and James Robinson cited pairs of countries, like North Korea and South Korea to support their argument that “it is man-made political and economic institutions that underlie economic success.”³⁸ Kaufmann et al (2000), observe that the ‘decline’ in the standard of living has been a result of “weak governance in the form of ineffective rule of law, inadequate protection of property rights, widespread corruption, and ill-advised policymaking serving special interests.”³⁹ According to Khan & Senhadji (2000), poor governance by African countries has led to poor economic growth since it affects negatively investment, productivity, foreign Aid, and consumption among others.⁴⁰ For Ghana to achieve sustainable growth and escape the dawning middle-income trap, the key elements of good governance—accountability, transparency, predictability, responsiveness, equity, and inclusion—must be in place. Shimomura and Yasutami (2003), highlight the crucial relationship between good governance and sustainable development.⁴¹ Fighting corruption would salvage the ‘dying’ Ghanaian economy which suffers from mismanagement and embezzlement. Building a more robust set of institutions based on laws, predictable, equitable, and accountable would also serve as a regulatory framework for public policies. The country must ensure that all six indicators of good governance⁴² are fully in force in order to drive the country towards the path of development. Dealing with the pervasive public corruption, structuring and strengthening state institutions to be more efficient could help set the country on the course of growth.

Moreover, there is a **need for inclusive growth**. Berg and Ostry (2011) observe that growth needs to be inclusive in order to be sustainable and effective in reducing poverty.⁴³ Indeed, according to Ostry, David, Berg, and Tsangarides,

³⁷ Kwon, Huck-ju, and Eunju Kim (2014). Poverty reduction and good governance: examining the rationale of the Millennium Development Goals. *Development and Change*, vol. 45, Issue 2.

³⁸ Acemoglu, Daron, and James A. Robinson. *Why nations fail: The origins of power, prosperity, and poverty*. Currency, 2012.

³⁹ Kaufmann, Daniel, Aart Kraay, and Pablo Zoido-Lobaton. "Governance matters: From measurement to action." *Finance and development* 37.2 (2000): 10.

⁴⁰ Khan, M. S., & Senhadji, A. S. (2000). *Financial development and economic growth: An overview* (IMF Working Paper No.00/209)

⁴¹ Shimomura, Yasutami. "In search of endogenous elements of good governance: The case of the Eastern seaboard development plan in Thailand." *The role of governance in Asia 2* (2003): 166-189.

⁴² The Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI): Voice and Accountability; Political Stability and absence of violence/terrorism; Government Effectiveness; Regulatory Quality; Rule of Law; Control of Corruption.

⁴³ Berg, A., and J. Ostry. "Inequality and Unstable Growth: Two Sides of the Same Coin?." IMF Staff Discussion Note, IMF, <http://imf.org/external/pubs/ft/sdn/2011/sdn1108.pdf> (2011).

one cannot separate “issues of economic growth and stability on one hand and equality on the other.”⁴⁴ In the views of Wan, Lu, and Chen (2006), ‘rising inequality in any country could have devastating effects on its growth in various ways.’⁴⁵ Inclusive growth through access to education, employment, and healthcare opportunities would help address and eradicate the vast socio-economic deprivations and high inequality among various segments of Ghanaian society. All traces of gender inequality must be eradicated to pave way for equal access to opportunities. Improved access to education, for example, would enhance human capital which would, in turn, result in high productivity. There should be social inclusion to enhance equal access to economic opportunities, and social safety to reduce the effects of transitory livelihood shocks, thereby preventing poverty. Ghana needs to create enough adequately paying jobs that can support individuals and families and lift them above the poverty line. They can do that by raising the minimum wage rate as well as creating good jobs. The government should put in measures and policies to continually sensitize its citizens about the importance of hard work and determination, as they are two of the strongest policies behind China’s success in lifting millions of its citizens from poverty. Lastly, to curb poverty in Ghana, there is an urgent need for the government to as well build assets and resources for lower-income communities. Leaders must make their priorities right and make sure that social protection is among them. They should increase the enforcement of existing laws against gender-based employment discrimination. In addition, there should be an increased promotion of mentorship and other efforts to boost the number of women in positions of political leadership. The agenda for eliminating the wage gap should be pushed for equal wages to be paid for the same job position regardless of one’s gender. More so, women empowerment programs should be intensified. Doing all of these will promote inclusive growth towards escaping the middle-income trap.

Concomitantly, there is the need for ‘**planned**’ investment in ‘**advanced**’ infrastructure—both social and physical—in order to set the stage for economic sustainability and reduce social inequalities. Kohli et al (2010) observe that sufficient infrastructure is indispensable in the bid for sustainable growth in Latin America.⁴⁶ Agénor, Pierre-Richard, and Otaviano argue that ‘improved access to advanced infrastructure may help to escape from the middle-income trap.’⁴⁷ Expedient investment in infrastructure would help draw growth, reduce inequality and enhance poverty reduction. For instance, road networks (physical infrastructure) would help in the transportation of goods and services, and enhance the smooth running of economic activities thereby bringing growth. Ghana could cooperate with Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), for example, to provide some of the most pressing infrastructural needs. The Availability of such infrastructure would also create equal opportunities for all to enhance their skills, engage in profitable ventures, be productive and contribute to national growth.

⁴⁴ Ostry, Mr Jonathan David, Mr Andrew Berg, and Mr Charalambos G. Tsangarides. *Redistribution, inequality, and growth*. International Monetary Fund, 2014.

⁴⁵ Wan, G., M. Lu, and Z. Chen. “The Inequality-Growth Nexus in the Short and Long Run: Empirical Evidence from China,” *Journal of Comparative Economics* 34(4) (2006): 654–667.

⁴⁶ Kohli, Harpaul, and Phillip Basil. “Infrastructure needs for a resurgent Latin America.” *Emerging Markets Forum*, 2010.

⁴⁷ Agénor, Pierre-Richard, and Otaviano Canuto. “Middle-income growth traps.” *Research in Economics* 69.4 (2015): 641-660.

Finally, there is a need for economic transformation, diversification, and industrialization in the context of ‘clean’ and ‘green growth.’ Homi Kharas and Harinder Kohli argue that countries need “innovation and product differentiation to meet the needs of the market” in order to avoid the middle-income trap.⁴⁸ Until the discovery of crude oil in recent years, Ghana’s economy has been agrarian-based—mainly in the production of Cocoa. Innovative transformation, diversification, and industrialization would not only offer job opportunities to the teeming youth but also, it would expand the revenue base of the country, making it less susceptible to economic shocks. Ghana needs to embrace high-tech technology manufacturing in a more environmentally friendly way, protecting the natural resource base of the country. For this to be successful, investment in education, training, IT, and new technologies would be a prerequisite. Equally important is that this economic transformation must be environmentally friendly, thus “clean” and “green growth” is a must for Ghana. Pushing for substantial economic transformation in the innovative and capital-intensive economy is a must for low-income countries (LICs), like Ghana, if they hope to achieve sustainable growth and evade the lurking middle-income Trap.

Conclusion

To sum it all up, Ghana can and must evade the middle-income trap. If Ghana hopes to achieve high income and prosperity, and endeavor to escape the looming middle-income trap, the fundamental drivers—governance and institutions; ‘planned’ investment in ‘advanced’ infrastructure (both social and physical); economic transformation, diversification, and industrialization in the context of ‘clean’ and ‘green growth and the prioritization of inclusive growth—must be at play in order to drive the desired growth.

Ghana has seen notable economic growth over the last decades. The country’s economic projections and indicators are usually positive.

⁴⁸ Kharas, Homi, and Harinder Kohli. “What Is the Middle Income Trap, Why Do Countries Fall into It, and How Can It Be Avoided?” *Global Journal of Emerging Market Economies*, vol. 3, no. 3, Sept. 2011, pp. 281–289, doi:10.1177/097491011100300302.

Figure 7: Real GDP Growth (Annual percent change)

Source: World Economic Outlook (April 2019)

As depicted in the above figure, the IMF in April 2019 projected Ghana to be the world's fastest-growing economy in 2019. This was because of the country's comeback after having experienced a serious economic crisis; impoverished and suffering famine about 30 years before. Ghana's economy has successfully recovered from the COVID-19-generated go-slow. ⁴⁹With the World Bank's projections, the country's economic growth is expected to be broad-based in 2022 and projected to reach 5.5% in 2022.⁵⁰

In terms of stability, it ranks very high among countries on the African continent and in the world, making it a suitable ground for FDIs. However, Accra faces many developmental challenges ranging from the mundane to the uncustomary. Despite these contradictions, all past and present governments are determined to steer the country towards a sustainable economic boom and achieve middle-income status, but not without first dealing with the lurking trap that comes with it. In order to escape the snares, this paper has suggested the need to embrace good governance and the building of strong institutions, prioritization of inclusive growth, investment in infrastructure, economic transformation, diversification, and industrialization in the context of 'green growth.'

However, a critical question of whether or not sustainability and economic growth (sustainable development) are mutually exclusive or not must first be addressed. From the time of the industrial revolution to the present, it is undeniable that as nations continue to grow their economies and improve the living standards of their citizens, their environmental footprint increases as well. Thus, the price of economic development has become environmental pollution. China, for example, has been able to lift more than six hundred million people from poverty over the last decades – a feat that no other country has been able to achieve. Yet, it came with a high environmental price, which the central

⁴⁹ World Economic Outlook, April 2019. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/05/ghana-is-set-to-be-the-worlds-fastest-growing-economy-this-year-according-to-the-imf/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/ghana/overview>

government continues to combat. Indeed, Ghana's GDP over the years keeps increasing, but it is also an undeniable fact that the country's Green House Gas (GHG) emissions are rising in tandem with economic growth. Globally, research has shown that climate change is real, and although some people might argue that climate will always change, they can hardly counter the fact that human actions, at least, hasten the process. Some researchers have suggested that the earth has entered the period of "Anthropocene" – an epoch where human activities are seen to be a dominant factor affecting the environment.⁵¹ How could nations reconcile sustainability with economic development when, in fact, for every growth rate achieved, humanity pushes the earth further towards destruction? How could nations achieve middle-income status and avoid the trap with the promise of "clean and green growth," when in reality, it is business as usual? These questions need further research and discussion.

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⁵¹ Lucy E. Edwards. "What Is the Anthropocene?" <https://eos.org/opinions/what-is-the-anthropocene>

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Ghana's scores in the corruption perception index by Transparency International

Appendix 2: GDP vs Population over the Years

Source: World Bank

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